

FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF FLAX/EPOXY COMPOSITE

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Keywords: *flax fibers, quasi-static, fatigue, P-S-N curves, biocomposite*

Abstract

The aim of this study is to analyze the fatigue response of a flax reinforced composite. The laminates were fabricated from noncrimp dry flax fabric impregnated with an epoxy matrix and stacked under pressure. Tensile and in-plane shear specimens having $[0/90]_{3S}$ and $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ sequences respectively, were tested to measure the quasi-static properties. A moderate properties scattering of around 10 % was found. The fatigue tests were performed from 80% to 40% of the composite ultimate quasi-static tensile strengths (UTS). Established Wohler's curves fit well with the Stress-Number of cycles (S-N) behaviour of this biomaterial. Classical three-stage stiffness degradation with a total loss of 15 to 20 % was observed on $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ specimens, while the stiffness evolution for $[0/90]_{3S}$ specimens revealed an increase of around 2 to 3 % of the material's stiffness.

1 Introduction

The interest in environmentally friendly materials is continuously increasing due to the raise of a global ecological consciousness. One alternative is to integrate biodegradable or recyclable reinforcement in composite material, instead of conventional manmade enhancement fibre, such as carbon, glass... Particularly, certain natural fibres, e.g. flax and hemp, can offer specific mechanical properties comparable to glass fibres due to their low density [1].

As natural fibres present important dispersions on their physical, mechanical and thermal properties, they are difficult to use for structural parts where a high reliability is usually required [2]. However, more and more studies related to natural fibres are carried out in the past few years. Among topics, investigated by authors, the mechanical properties

of single fibre [3], the optimization of process parameters of composite reinforced with vegetal fibre [4], the hydrophilic fibre/hydrophobic matrix interfacial adhesion improvement method [5], etc. are abundantly studied. Also, cyclic or fatigue investigation on elementally fibres can also be found in the literature. Baley [3] has highlighted the increase of the Young's modulus of flax fibres in tensile and cyclic loading. The stiffness of a single fibre can rise from 40 GPa up to nearly 70 GPa. Placet [6] in his study reported a storage modulus increase of 60 % on hemp fibre during dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). Silva et al. [7] were interested in the fatigue behaviour of sisal fibres. Authors found that at a fatigue stress below 50 % UTS, all tested hemp fibres resist 10^6 cycles. A slight increase of hysteresis slope, which suggested an increase on fibre's Young's modulus was observed. More recently, investigations on the fatigue behaviour of bio-sourced composites reinforced with natural fibres were carried out. In particular, Towo and Ansell [8] have studied the effect of chemical treatment on unidirectional (UD) sisal fibre impregnated in epoxy and polyester matrix. Treated laminates with PMMA exhibited a slight improvement on the composites' fatigue resistance. Moderate raise of the composites' initial rigidity is remarked in the tension-tension fatigue test.

Despite of the great interest on biocomposite material, only a few studies focus on their fatigue response. So this paper presents the results of the experimental study of the fatigue behaviour of a flax/epoxy composite.

2 Material and experimental test

2.1 Materials

The specimens were made of a flax reinforcement of Hermès variety cultivated in northern France.

Commercial dry roller of non-crimp flax fabric is provided by a local textile company CRST. The balanced fabric consists of two identical layers of UD fibres oriented perpendicularly one relative to another. The layers are stitched together using a cotton thread. The cotton's surface weight is 2 g/m² and the distance between two parallel stitch lines is 10 mm. The average areal weight of the flax fabric (including the thread) is 235 g/m². The fabrics are used as received, no further treatment is applied. Matrix is an epoxy system based on the resin SR 8200 with corresponding standard hardener SR 8205 ordered from SICOMIN (France). Densities of resin and hardener at 20 °C are 1.175 and 1.039 g/cm³, respectively.

2.2 Specimens preparation

Fabric layers were first cut from the roller and manually impregnated with a liquid resin-hardener mixture, and then the plies were stacked in a hydraulic press equipped with heating plates. The assembly is heated at a rate of 2 °C/min. The curing is realized at a stable temperature of 60 °C during 8 hours with a stacking pressure of 7 bars applied to the plates.

Two laminate types having [0/90]_{3S} and [±45]_{3S} stacking sequences were fabricated for tensile and in-plane shear tests respectively.

2.3 Quasi-static tests

Fig. 1. Tensile and in-plane shear specimen configuration; unit: mm.

Rectangular specimens of 250 mm long, 25 mm wide (*b*) and around 2.2 mm thick (*t*) were cut from laminate plate. Specimens' ends were equipped with 50 mm long aluminium end-tabs, as illustrated in Fig. 1. *x* and *y* axes are designated as the longitudinal loading and transverse direction respectively. Strain gauge rosette with two perpendicular elements of 5 mm long, from KYOWA company is glued to the middle of the specimens' surface. The testing machine is a servo-

hydraulic MTS 809 with a capacity of 100 kN. The crosshead speed was 2 mm/min. In order to control the testing temperature at 23 °C, the tests were carried out in a Servatin thermal chamber. The experimental measurements were recorded at 10 Hz quasi-static frequency with a data acquisition system.

The uniaxial tensile tests on [0/90]_{3S} specimens were conducted according to the ISO 527-4 standard. The in-plane shear tests ([±45]_{3S} specimens) were performed according to the ISO 14129 standard. The specimen configuration (Fig. 1) and testing condition were similar to tensile tests conditions. Indeed, the shear stress and strain (τ_{12}, γ_{12}) measured from the tensile loading of [±45]_{3S} specimen are given by Eq.1 and Eq.2. 1 and 2 directions correspond to fibres orientations. *F* and *b*×*t* represents the applied load and the specimen's cross-section, respectively. ϵ is the recorded strain.

$$\tau_{12} = F / (2b \times t) \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma_{12} = \epsilon_x - \epsilon_y \quad (2)$$

The quasi-static tests were carried out without humidity control. Five specimens were tested in each case to figure out their scattering aspect.

2.3 Fatigue tests

Fatigue tests on [0/90]_{3S} and [±45]_{3S} specimens, were carried out based on ISO 130003 standard [9]. Specimen geometry, testing machine and temperature control are identical to quasi-static test. Tension-tension fatigue tests were conducted under sinusoidal load amplitude control mode with a loading ratio of *R* = 0.1. Five stress levels ranging from 40 to 80 % UTS were foreseen and a least of 5 replicate tests were performed at each stress level. For both loadings, the test frequency was 5 Hz. Test was stopped at specimen failure or at 2×10⁶ cycles endurance limit.

The MTS 809 testing machine is equipped with a crosshead displacement sensor (Δl), with 0.003 mm resolution corresponding to a strain precision ($\Delta l / l_0$) of 0.002 % in the specimens ($l_0 = 150$ mm). The accuracy of the strain data is

enough satisfactory for the study. Thus, strain measurements were calculated based on the ratio of crosshead displacement to the specimen length.

3 Results and discussion

Fibre volume fraction (V_f) was determined by specimen volume and weight measurement according to ASTM standard [10]. $V_f = 43.7 \pm 1.5\%$ with a void volume fraction estimated at $1.3 \pm 0.8\%$. The small variation of V_f indicates a good reproducibility of the fabrication process.

3.1 Quasi-static behaviour

The tensile and in-plane shear tests results are given in Tab. 1. The data in brackets are the coefficient of variation (in percentage). The maximum shear strain is estimated by correlating quasi-static data from gauges with the displacement of the machine crosshead. In accordance with shear standard, the specimen maximum shear stress considered is corresponding to the 5 % shear strain.

Tensile properties	[0/90] _{3S}	[±45] _{3S}
Young’s modulus (GPa)	14.6 (4.2%)	6.5 (10%)
Poisson’s ratio	0.17 (29%)	0.75 (4.7%)
Tensile strength (MPa)	170 (10%)	79 (8.3%)
Strain at failure (%)	1.72 (7.6%)	3.8 (16%)
In-plane shear properties*		
Shear modulus (GPa)	1.87 (8.1%)	
Shear strength (MPa)	40 (8.3%)	
Shear strain at failure (%)	6.23 (17%)	

Tab. 1. Quasi-static properties of flax/epoxy laminate.*the in-plane shear properties are extracted from [±45]_{3S} tensile test.

With the exception of the Poisson’s ratio and ultimate shear strain, the scattering of the quasi-static properties of the flax reinforced laminate is in the same range than the glass fibre based composite [11]. The composite variability is much lower than that of elementary flax fibre, where the scattering of

Young’s modulus and tensile strength are 28 and 36 % respectively according to [3]. This can be explained by an averaging effect in the composite. The overall behaviour of the reinforcements creates compensation effects on the disparities between fibres, inducing lower dispersion on laminate’s scale.

The tensile properties of the [±45]_{3S} specimens are given in Tab. 1. The fatigue loading levels were calculated based on these results.

3.2 Fatigue behaviour

The fatigue loading frequency was studied before conducting the fatigue test program in order to ensure the best compromise between the self-heating of the specimens and the time consuming of experimental work. Indeed, the standard [9] requires a test frequency causing a temperature increase lower than 10 °C during endurance test. The preliminary study showed an overall satisfaction of 5 Hz testing frequency. Further more, the thermal chamber played a favourable role in controlling the testing temperature.

Loading level	[0/90] _{3S}	[±45] _{3S}
80 %	1847 (1574)	2962 (3549)
70 %	12024 (10128)	19170 (18042)
60 %	79220 (73998)	295804 (212900)
50 %	177387 (132462)	> 2×10 ⁶
40 %	1154067 (500909)	> 2×10 ⁶

Tab. 2. Fatigue life of flax/epoxy laminate, unit: number of cycles.

$$Lg(N) = A - B\sigma + Cs \tag{3}$$

Tab. 2 gives the fatigue life of around 100 specimens, in number of cycles, with standard deviation in bracket. The S-N curves of the two stacking sequences are plotted in Fig. 2. [±45]_{3S} specimens sustaining more than 2×10⁶ cycles are symbolized by points with arrows. It is noticeable that [0/90]_{3S} specimens undergo higher loading stress than [±45]_{3S} ones for a same number of cycles. This is coherent with the quasi-static properties. The

overall scattering seems decreasing with the fatigue life. The predict model is a modified Wohler's curves (Eq. 3), where N is the number of cycles to failure, A and B are intrinsic parameter of the material, σ is the maximum stress applied, C is the number of standard deviation (s) related to the confident level. In Eq. 3, for C equals to 0 and -2 corresponding to the survival probabilities of $P=50\%$ and 98% respectively, are fitted to experimental data in Fig. 2, according to [12].

Fig. 2. S-N behaviour of $[0/90]_{3S}$ and $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ flax/epoxy specimens.

The typical behaviour of $[0/90]_{3S}$ and $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ flax/epoxy specimens are presented in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. Fig. 3 shows the early and last hysteresis loops of $[0/90]_{3S}$ and $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ specimens loaded at 80% UTS. Throughout the tests, the loops move towards higher strains for constant stress level. Because the mean load is superior to zero, the loading creep occurs, inducing a shift of the loop with the loading cycles to higher strain. The residual strain corresponding to the minimum stress in each loop increases with the number of cycles. This phenomenon is noticed for both lay-ups at all load levels. Nevertheless, the kinetic is different as shown in Fig. 4. A three-stage development is observed on $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ specimens. The plot rises at the beginning with a slowing down of the evolution rate. This stage is followed by a quasi-linear during an important ratio of specimens' life. Finally an acceleration phase occurs with a local shrinking effect. As to the $[0/90]_{3S}$ samples, with few exception, the two previous first stages are present.

No acceleration is noticed, suggesting a brittle behaviour at failure.

Fig. 3. Hysteresis loops of the first ($n/N_f = 0$) and last ($n/N_f = 1$) cycles of 80% UTS tests.

Fig. 4. Strain at minimum stress for $[0/90]_{3S}$ and $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ specimens at 80% UTS tests.

The evolution of the specimen's stiffness gives indication of the materials damage. Generally, its decrease with the fatigue loading cycles is wildly used as an indicator of material degradation. Fig. 5 shows typical evolutions of the normalized modulus progression E with respect to average modulus measured during the first cycles E_0 . The stiffness of the $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ specimens decreases in three stages, as described by Case and Reifsnider [13]. An initial stage with rapid stiffness reduction due to micro cracks in the material until saturation. This phase is then followed by an intermediate region with a steady further decrease of the stiffness,

corresponding to more matrix cracking, edge effects and delamination. Finally, fibre breakage, matrix cracking and interply delamination lead to the failure. Conversely, in the case of $[0/90]_{3S}$ specimens, the stiffness increases with the number of cycles of around 2 %, and then remains stable until failure. This indicates a stiffening phenomenon of the material.

Fig. 5. Strain at minimum stress of the $[0/90]_{3S}$ and $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ specimens at 80% UTS tests.

The tensile stiffness increase of natural fibres has been described in [6][7]. Within the microstructure of the reinforcement, Baley [3] found that the flax fibre is composed of four concentric cylinders among which the cylinder S2 consists of highly crystalline cellulose fibrils spirally wound in a matrix of amorphous hemicelluloses and lignin with an angle of around 10° to the fibre axis. These cellulose fibrils tend to straighten when the fibre is loaded along its axis, resulting in the increase of Young’s modulus. All elementary natural fibres submitted to fatigue or cyclic tests (e.g. flax, sisal, hemp) exhibited strong stiffness increase. In the case of flax/epoxy laminates having $[0/90]_{3S}$ cross plies stacking sequence, half of the flax fibres are loaded in their axis direction. The rearrangement of the microfibrils can be responsible of the stiffening effect measured. Towo and Ansell [8] explained the slight improvement of Young’s modulus of UD sisal fibre reinforced composite by the rearrangement of the microfibrils.

The elongation of the specimens, indicated by the increase of the residual strain because of creep effect, may also include the straightening of the

microfibrils. Indeed, samples’ elongation during fatigue loading can be explained by to the stretching of flax fibres. Because of their structure (non-homogeneity, defects, geometric variability...), the fibres cannot be straight as manmade ones. The fibres are naturally wavy and may realign with fatigue solicitation. Thus, this contribution in the specimen elongation is non negligible. On the other hand, the reorientation phenomenon can create a gain of modulus.

It’s important to note that, during one single fibre fatigue test, considerable stiffening (up to 60%) is observed [6], while only 2-3% of stiffness increase is generally measured for the $[0/90]_{3S}$ specimens (Fig. 5). Indeed, with a fibre volume fraction is 43%, knowing that only a half of them are loaded in their axis direction because the cross ply stacking sequence and important scatter of fibre strength resulting in early fibre breakage, global stiffness increase is pulled down. The laminate, the matrix degradation, is compensated by the fibre stiffening in $[0/90]_{3S}$ case. Globally, the combination of complex effects leads to a laminate final stiffness increase much less important than for single fibre.

Fig. 6. General stiffness evolution. T for Tensile $[0/90]_{3S}$ and S for tensile $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ specimens.

The overall stiffness development for all loading levels of the two stacking sequences is plotted in Fig. 6. Each curve is a real representative data for a given loading condition. The scattering bars enclose all the curves tested in the same conditions (level of loading and stacking sequence). Considering the variability for different samples, one can conclude that the evolution of stiffness is independent of the

loading level. Fig. 6 reveals that the modulus of $[0/90]_{3S}$ specimens increases up to 2~3 %, followed by a stable stage until the failure occur. In the particular case of specimens loaded at 40 % UTS, plots show a stiffness decrease stage before breakage. The three-stage stiffness degradation is confirmed for $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ specimens. A steep decrease of modulus happens at early stage, then the second phase lasts a relative long time, i.e. $0.3 < n/N_f < 0.8$, thirdly, an acceleration stage occurs with a total loss of stiffness of 15 ~ 20 %.

4 Conclusion

This paper presents experimental investigations in quasi-static and fatigue loading of flax fibre reinforced epoxy laminates. The study highlighted the following points:

- The scattering of the composite's mechanical properties is much less than for elementary flax fibre. The variability is comparable to glass/polyester material because of an average effect. This suggests that vegetal fibres sourced composites can offer similar reliability level than conventional composites.
- Creep effect during fatigue test is observed. The hysteresis shifting kinetic reveals a necking effect occurring in $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ specimens. $[0/90]_{3S}$ specimens exhibit brittle behaviour.
- Classical three-stage stiffness degradation is observed on $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ specimens. Contrary, a stiffening phenomenon of 2~3 % is remarked for $[0/90]_{3S}$ ones, in which half of the reinforcement is loaded along the fibre axis. This increase in specimen modulus contributes to straighten the fibres and to rearrange the microfibrils inside the flax fibre structure.
- Stiffness evolution with life ratio is independent of the fatigue loading level.

Acknowledgements

The financial support of the Faber fund from the Bourgogne Region, France is gratefully acknowledged.

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